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Filament Winding Path Design Based on Layer-by-layer Update of the Mandrel Profiles

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The aim of research

In filament winding process the fiber trajectories are various when the composite layers update ; therefore, the fiber trajectories obtained by the original mandrel profile affect the precise of filament winding path.

In present study a method was employed to obtained the accurate winding path, and the influence of composite layers update on the performance factor(PV/W) of pressure vessels was investigated.

The mandrel profiles change with the composite layers that update every for plies in the experiments

Methods

In order to obtain the accurate winding path, the laser scanner was used to obtain the mandrel profiles that update by layer-by-layer, and the CadWind was employed to calculate new winding patterns, as shown in the right figures.

Filament winding experiments

- Experiments

1. Liner

The aluminum liner 6061-T6 was used to experiments. Owing to the unequal dome parts, the filament winding experiments were carried out based on non-geodesic trajectories.

2. Experimental process

Laser scanner

Scanning the liner

Mandrel profile after scanning

Online scanning

Results

In order to investigate the variety of the winding angle when the composite layers update, the experiments of updating profiles by every two and four plies were carried out. The results are shown in the following figures.

Winding angle of the dome part 1 obtained by updating every two plies

Winding angle of the dome part 2 obtained by updating every two plies

Winding angle of the dome part 1 obtained by updating every four plies

Winding angle of the dome part 2 obtained by updating every two plies

The variety of the winding angle at the equator when the mandrel profiles update by every two plies

Plies	1-2	3-4	5-6	7-8	9-10	11-12
Winding angle at the equator(°)	13	13.1	13.1	13.3	13.5	13.5
Accuracy (%)	0	0.7	0.7	2	3.8	3.8

The variety of the winding angle at the equator when the mandrel profiles update by every four plies

The winding angle obtained by updating every four plies has an obvious change in the polar opening compared to that computed by updating every two plies.

Plies	1-4	5-8	9-12	13-16
Winding angle at the equator(°)	13	14	14	14.2
Accuracy (%)	0	7.7	7.7	9

Conclusions:

As the mandrel profiles update, the winding angle at the equator do not have a significant change. However, compared to the mandrel profiles not updated the accuracy of the winding angle obtained by updating mandrel profiles is improved.

With the updating plies increase the variety of the winding angle at the equator is apparent.

Numerical simulation

According to the results of filament winding experiments, the mandrel profile updated by every four plies was utilized for numerical simulation to investigate the influence of updating plies on the performance factor of the pressure vessel.

- **Progressive failure analysis**

Results of the mandrel without updating plies

Displacement of the cylinder section under the pressure of 120MPa

Conclusion: the burst pressure is 84MPa

(a) Fiber failure in longitudinal direction

(c) Matrix failure in normal direction

(b) Matrix failure in transverse direction

(d) Shear failure

Displacement of the cylinder section under the pressure of 160MPa

Results of the mandrel with updating plies

Conclusion: the burst pressure is 88MPa and the performance factor is compared between the two pressure vessels, as shown in follows.

	Burst pressure (MPa)	Volume (L)	Mass (Kg)	Performance factor(PV/W,Km)	Increase proportion (%)
Pressure vessel without updating plies	84	6.8	2.932	19.48	5.18
Pressure vessel with updating plies	88	6.8	2.92	20.49	

THE END

Thank you for attention